

Preparation of N-aryl, N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidines : I. The appropriate guanidine sulphate (0.1 mole) α - ω dibromoalkane (0.2 mole) and pyridine (0.15 mole) were refluxed by means of an oilbath for a period of about 3 to 4 hours. The mixture was then poured in ice-cold water. The aqueous layer was separated and washed with ether. It was then neutralized by adding sodium bicarbonate. Free base was separated as precipitates upon vigorous scratching. It was then filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from ethanol. The yield was in the range of 55-70% of the theoretical amount.

Preparation of N-aryl, N'(ω -mercapto)alkyl guanidine : II. N-aryl-N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidine (0.01 mole) and sodium hydrogen sulphide (0.01 mole) were dissolved in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for about half an hour on water-bath. Sodium bromide separated on cooling, was filtered off and the filtrate on standing gave the crystals of the mercapto compound. It was filtered, dried and recrystallized from rectified spirit. The yield was about 70% of the theoretical amount.

Preparation of N-aryl, N'(ω -thiosulphuro) alkyl guanidines (Bunte Salts) : III. The hydrobromide salt of N-aryl, N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidine (0.01 mole) and sodium thiosulphate crystals (0.01 mole) were dissolved in slightly more than the required amount of warm water, then refluxed for about half an hour and filtered. The crystals of the Bunte salt were obtained on cooling. The yield was about 80-90% of the theoretical amount.

Preparation of Isothiuronium salts : IV. Equimolar amounts of N-aryl, N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidine and thiourea were dissolved in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for about 15 minutes on water-bath. The solution was then concentrated to half of its volume, cooled and diluted with equal volume of ethyl acetate. The mixture was then chilled, stirred and scratched to give the crystals of isothiuronium salt.

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Palladium(II) Complexes of α -Oximino-acetoacetarylamide Benzoylhydrazones

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IN continuation of our previous work on synthesis of α -oximino- β -hydrazinoacetoacetarylamides¹, their analytical aspects²⁻⁴ and Pd(II) complexes⁵, the present paper deals with the preparation and characterisation of Pd(II) complexes with α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide benzoylhydrazones.

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes : 10 ml. aq. solution of Pd(II) chloride (0.05 M) was gradually added to 25 ml alcoholic solution (2%) of α -oximinoacetoacetylchloroanilide benzoylhydrazone and acidified with dil. HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and digested on waterbath for half an hour; the bright yellow precipitates obtained were filtered, washed with hot water and aq. ethanol (1:1), and dried in an oven at 110°.

The Pd(II) complexes of the other α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide benzoylhydrazones of the series were prepared in the same manner. The m.p., colour, elemental analysis and composition of the complexes are given in Table-1. The infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes and the electronic spectra of the ligands in ethanol solution were recorded.

Results and Discussion

Electronic spectra of the ligands : The chromophoric system N=C-C-C=O in the ligands exhibits two

bands, one at 230-35 nm (C=18500-27400) and second at 275-79 nm (C=16500-20300). Comparison of these spectra with those of acetoacetarylamide benzoylhydrazones with chromophoric system, N=C-CH₂-C=O (Band I, 250-258 nm, C=15100 to 26400, Band II, 229-230 nm, C=16100 to 17200)⁶ reveals that there is hypsochromic effect (Δ C=1800-3900) in Band I and there is a bathochromic displacement of the Band II to the extent of 46-50 nm, without appreciable change in intensity.

TABLE I—PALLADIUM COMPLEXES OF α -OXIMINOACETARYLAMIDE BENZOYLHYDRAZONES

No.	R	Composition	Colour	m p. °C (decomp.)	% Palladium		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	Golden yellow	360	13.74	13.67	14.30	14.35
2	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₈ N ₈ Cl ₂ Pd	Bright „	320	12.44	12.98	13.80	13.63
3	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₈ N ₈ Cl ₂ Pd	„ „	325	12.83	12.98	13.63	13.79
4	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	Golden „	300	13.30	13.12	13.85	13.78
5	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	Orange	327	13.16	13.12	13.72	13.78
6	<i>m</i> -2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	Golden yellow	330	13.31	13.19	13.91	13.85
7	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₈ N ₈ Cl ₂ Pd	Bright „	305	12.92	12.98	13.78	13.63
8	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	Orange red	320	12.55	12.69	13.27	13.32

Infrared spectra: The important infrared spectral bands and their assignments are based on the study of the free ligands and their Pd(II) complexes. The strong band at 3480-3500 cm⁻¹ appears in the ligands but does not appear in the corresponding complexes. This suggests the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bond in the ligands. This band is within the expected region for intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁷. The absence of such band in the complexes is the indication of the replacement of hydrogen of oximino group by metal ion. The strong band at 990-1005 cm⁻¹ in the ligands is attributed to N-O stretch. In the complexes this band shifts to 1170-1180 cm⁻¹. The N-O stretches of nitrogen and oxygen coordinated oximino groups are expected to shift to higher and lower frequencies respectively compared to that of the ligands. The increase in N-O frequency shows the coordination through nitrogen of oximino group. This further agrees with the usual behaviour of oximino group to coordinate through nitrogen atom⁸⁻¹¹. According to Sterk and Ziegler (C=N, 1625 cm⁻¹)¹², the strong band around 1590-1615 cm⁻¹ in the ligands indicates C=N stretching frequency. In the complexes this band appears around 1570-1600 cm⁻¹. The lowering of the C=N stretching frequency is an indication of the coordination of 1-nitrogen of benzoyl hydrazide. The infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes reveal bands of strong, medium or weak intensity around 3300, 3070 and 3440 cm⁻¹ indicating secondary trans association and free N-H vibrations of amides respectively¹³.

From the spectra it is evident that ligands as well as complexes in the solid state are mostly in the associated form. The probable associations are due to hydrogen bonding between carbonyl groups and hydrogen of the amide and benzylhydrazide moieties. The strong band around 3300 cm⁻¹ is considered to be due to trans associated form. The strong bands in the ligands and complexes around 1655 and 1680 cm⁻¹, 1550 and 1530 cm⁻¹ and 1300 and 1260 cm⁻¹ are attributed to amide I, amide II and amide III bands, as associated and free forms respectively¹³.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Hydrolysis of Sec. Amyl Bromide in Neutral Medium

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FEW compounds,^{1,3,4,5,6,7} in the alkyl halide series, have been investigated to show the olefin elimination kinetically independent of simultaneous substitution in alkaline medium, but the literature regarding the studies to show the kinetic dependence of olefin elimination and substitution processes which occur simultaneously in the solvolysis of halides is scanty. The present investigation mainly deals with the kinetic dependence of both processes which simultaneously occur in neutral hydrolysis of sec-amyl bromide. Olefin elimination and simultaneous substitution reactions both followed first order with respect to the halide. Total first order rate constant has been split up into its constituents (Olefin elimination and substitution rate constant) by suitable measurement of olefin formed. The present investigation also includes the effect of change in the composition of the medium on the rate of reactions, calculation of separate energies of activation in both processes, effect of salt on rate of reaction. In the present case, the unimolecular processes may take place through the scheme given by Moelwyn-Hughes and Fells⁸.

Experimental

Sec-amyl bromide was dried over anhydrous sodium carbonate and calcium chloride and then fractionated. The fraction collected at 11 °-118° (B.P.) was used for all measurements.

The value of first order rate constant was determined by estimating the acid produced as a result of hydrolysis of halide at various intervals of time and by

employing the usual integrated formula for first order. The olefin was estimated by the following method. The sealed ampule containing 5 ml. of the reaction mixture was first cooled and then broken by shaking under water at 0° in an evacuated stoppered flask provided with an inlet and outlet tube, the former reaching the bottom. The flask was kept at 50°-60° in a water bath and the whole amount of olefin produced was swept by passing a slow stream of nitrogen and bubbling the gas in a flask containing a known amount of bromine in carbon tetrachloride. The remaining bromine was estimated by titrating it against standard thiosulphate. The substitution product was identified as sec-amyl alcohol by the method described earlier.^{8,4,5,6,7,10}

Results and Discussions

Experimental results are presented in Tables 1-2. Table 1 records the total first order rate constant

TABLE 1

Temperature (°C)	[EtOH-H ₂ O] (V/V %)	[KBr] × M	k', in min. ⁻¹ Limits of accuracy are ±2.7% or less. k', × 10 ⁵
[Sec-amyl bromide] = 7.97 × 10 ⁻³ M			
55	80	—	1.82
"	75	—	4.84 ^a
"	70	—	7.60
"	65	—	9.11 ^a
"	60	—	23.85
"	55	—	95.02
"	50	—	143.66 ^a
"	45	—	201.44
"	40	—	262.61
"	60	0.25	23.00
"	"	0.50	21.85 ^b
"	"	0.75	20.62 ^b
"	"	1.00	19.24
"	"	1.25	17.92
"	"	1.50	15.67 ^b
40	"	—	4.37 ^c
45	"	—	8.12 ^a
50	"	—	12.74
60	"	—	38.56 ^d
65	"	—	64.60 ^c
70	"	—	107.72 ^d
75	"	—	170.18 ^d

a: ±2.5%, b: ±1.2%, c: ±2.8%, d: ±3.6%.

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